

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Epidemiology, Etiology, Pathophysiology, Physiology, Pharmacotherapy, Treatment and Diagnosis

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 23 June 2025

Keywords:

Folic Acid, Lysine Hydrochloride, RP-HPLC, Synthetic mixture, Accuracy, Linearity and Precision

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15722410

ABSTRACT

Folic Acid is the water-soluble vitamin (vitamin B9) and lysine hydrochloride is Amino acid Supplement. Folic Acid and Lysine Hydrochloride used as Growth and Development of Children, folate deficiency, amino acid deficiency. Development and validation of simple, Precise and Accurate RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of Folic Acid and Lysine in synthetic mixture. The validation of this method was achieved as per ICH Q2 (R2) guidelines with the optimized experimental conditions. To achieve the proposed method on C18 column (250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m) column as Stationary Phase and run time was 30 min. The Mobile Phase consists of Methanol, Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (50:20:30). UV detection was carried out at 300nm. Linearity co-relation co-efficient found is Folic acid is 0.9993 and lysine hydrochloride is 0.9999. The method was validated by determining its accuracy, linearity and precision. The proposed method is simple, precise, economical and hence can be applied for routine quality control of Folic Acid and Lysine Hydrochloride in synthetic mixture.

INTRODUCTION

The chemical name of Dapagliflozin Folic Acid is N-(4-((2-amino-4-oxo-1,4-dihydropteridin-6-yl)methylamino)benzoyl)-L-glutamic acid and Lysine Hydrochloride chemical name is (S)-2,6-diaminohexanoic acid monohydrochloride. Folic acid (Vitamin B9) and lysine hydrochloride are

commonly combined in oral liquid formulations used as nutritional supplements. While folic acid plays a key role in DNA synthesis, cell division, and hematopoiesis, lysine hydrochloride, an essential amino acid, supports protein synthesis, immune function, and overall growth. Given their widespread use, especially in pediatric and nutritional applications, it is essential to establish

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

a robust method for their simultaneous estimation in combined formulations. Simultaneous estimation of compounds with distinct physicochemical properties, such as folic acid (a vitamin) and lysine hydrochloride (an amino acid salt), poses unique analytical challenges. These include differences in polarity, solubility, and UV absorbance, which require careful selection of chromatographic conditions to achieve proper resolution and detection. Reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) is a preferred analytical technique due to its high sensitivity, specificity, and suitability for a wide range of pharmaceutical compounds. This study

focuses on the development and validation of a simple, reliable, and reproducible RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of folic acid and lysine hydrochloride in their combined oral liquid formulation. The method was optimized for key parameters such as mobile phase composition, pH, flow rate, detection wavelength, and retention time to ensure adequate separation and quantification of both analytes. Validation of the developed method was performed in accordance with ICH Q2(R1) guidelines, evaluating parameters such as linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, and robustness.

Folic Acid

Lysine Hydrochloride

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Materials

Table 1.0 Materials & Sources

Sr. No.	Name of APIs	Source
1	Folic Acid	Orion Life Science

2	Lysine Hydrochloride	Mcdil Laboratories
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Instrumentation

- HPLC instrument with UV-visible detector
- Software: LC Solution

- Column - HYPERSIL ODS C18, 250 mm*4.6 mm
- UV-visible Spectrophotometer - SHIMADZU 1800 Software - UV probe, version- 2.42
- Digital Analytical Balance - Mettler Toledo
- Ultra Sonicator -PS 21
- Controlled temperature water bath
- Hot air Oven – Kesar
- FTIR – SHIMADZU
- Melting Point Apparatus – Gallenkamp Model: 889339

Chemicals and Reagents: Folic Acid API, Lysine Hydrochloride API, Acetonitrile HPLC Grade, Methanol HPLC Grade, Phosphate Buffer HPLC Grade and HPLC Grade water.

Preparation of Phosphate Buffer 0.05M: Weight accurately 9.8g of Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate, Transfer in 1000mL of volumetric flask add 700mL of distilled water sonicate properly and markup to volume.

Preparation of Mobile Phase: The mobile phase was prepared by adding the ratio of (50:20:30 v/v/v) Methanol: Acetonitrile: Buffer 0.05M (Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate) and then filtered through 0.45 µm membrane filter; sonicated for 15 min.

Preparation of Standard Stock Solution

Standard Stock Solution for Folic acid Propionate: Accurately weighed quantity of Folic acid Propionate 10 mg was transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 100 µg/mL. Withdraw 1 ml from Stock Solution and make up to 0.1 ml with to get 1 µg/mL.

Standard Stock Solution for Lysine Hydrochloride: Accurately weighed quantity of Lysine Hydrochloride 10 mg was transferred into 100 mL volumetric flask, dissolved in methanol and diluted up to mark with methanol. This will give a stock solution having strength of 100 µg/mL. Withdraw 7 ml from Stock Solution and make up to 10 ml with to get 70 µg/mL

Chromatographic Conditions:

Table 2.0 Chromatographic Conditions

Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (50:20:30 v/v/v)
Detection	300nm
Flow rate	1.5 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Detector	UV detector
Injection volume	10 µl
Column oven temperature	40°C
Mode:	ISOCRATIC

Identification And Characterization

The identification of taken standard API for experimental work had done for confirmation of its identity, standard quality and purity. The identification had done by taking IR and UV spectra, solubility study and melting point determination.

Solubility Study:

The solubility of Folic Acid & Lysine Hydrochloride practically determined separately by taking 100 mg of both the drugs in 100 ml volumetric flasks, adding required quantity of solvent at room temperature and shaken for few minutes. Solubility data for each study was observed and recorded in Table 4.0.

Table 3.0 Solubility Table

Description Terms	Relative Quantities of solvent for 1 Parts of solute
Very soluble	Less than 1 part
Freely soluble	From 1 to 10 parts
Soluble	From 10 to 30 parts
Sparingly soluble	From 30 to 100 parts
Slightly soluble	From 300 to 1000 parts
Very slightly soluble	From 1000 to 10000 parts

Practically Insoluble

More than 10000 parts

Table 4.0 Solubility Data for Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol

Solvent	Folic Acid	Bisoprolol
Water	Very Slightly soluble	Very soluble
Chloroform	Soluble	Non-Soluble
0.1 N HCL	Soluble	Highly Soluble
Acetonitrile	Very Soluble	Low Soluble
Methanol	Very Soluble	Slightly Soluble
Ethanol	Very Soluble	Less Soluble

Identification by Melting Point Determination:

points of the compounds were taken by open capillary method.

Melting point of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol hydrochloride has been determined. The melting

Table 5.0 Melting Point of Drugs

Sr. No.	APIs	Melting Point	
		Reported	Measured
1	Folic Acid	250-260°C	240-260 °C
2	Lysine Hydrochloride	260-265°C	263-264°C

IR Spectra:

following graph. IR Spectra scanning of sample: Lysine Hydrochloride.

The IR Spectra of Lysine Hydrochloride with its functional group identification, were shown in the

Fig 1.0 IR Spectra of Standard Lysine Hydrochloride

Table 6.0 IR Spectra Interpretation for Lysine Hydrochloride

Groups	General Range(cm-1)	Observed Range(cm-1)
N-H (s)	3400-3100	3164
C-H (s)	3000-2800	2866
COO ⁻ (a)	1650-1600	1667
NH ₃ ⁺ (b)	1580-1510	1581
C-N (s)	1200-1000	1667
NH ₃ ⁺ (r)	800-600	711

The IR Spectra of Folic Acid with its functional group identification, were shown in the following graph. IR Spectra scanning of sample: Folic Acid.

Table 7.0 IR Spectra Interpretation for Folic Acid

Groups	General Range(cm-1)	Observed Range(cm-1)
N-H (s)	3400-3200	3376
C-H (s)	3100-3000	2925
C=O (s)	1700-1650	1659
C=C(s)	1650-1550	1575
C-O(s)	1100-1000	1050

Method Development

Selection of Wavelength:

To determine wavelength for measurement, standard spectra of Folic acid & Lysine

Hydrochloride were scanned between 200-400 nm against diluents. Absorbance maxima of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride have detected at 300. Chromatogram was taken at 300 nm, both drugs

give good peak height and shape. So, 300 nm was selected for Simultaneous estimation of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride in their formulation.

Fig 3.0 Overlay UV Spectra of Lysine Hydrochloride and Folic Acid

Selection Of Column:

For RP-HPLC Method, various columns are available but based on literature survey C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm) was selected over the other columns.

Selection of Mobile phase:

Table 8.0 Trial 1: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :1	
Column	: C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	: Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (30:70v/v)
Detection	300nm
Flow rate	1mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	No peak observed

Fig 4. Trial 1: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer(30:90v/v)

Trial :2	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (50:50v/v)
Detection	300nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Only one peak detected byt broad peak observed

Table 9.0 Trial 2: Selection of Mobile Phase

Fig 5.0 Trial 2: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer(50:50v/v)

Table 10.0 Trial 3: selection of mobile phase

TRIAL :3	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer (80:20v/v)
Detection	300nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Only one peak detected byt broad peak observed

Fig. 6.0 Trial 3: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Acetonitrile: Phosphate Buffer(80:20v/v)

Table 11.0 Trial 4: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :4	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Methanol: Phosphate Buffer(60:40v/v)
Detection	300nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Only one peak detected

Fig 7.0 Trial 4: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Methanol: Phosphate Buffer(60:40v/v)

Table 12.0 Trial 5: selection of mobile phase

Trial :5	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Methanol: Phosphate Buffer (70:30v/v)
Detection	300nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Only one peak detected

Fig 8.0 Trial 5: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Methanol: Phosphate Buffer(70:30v/v)

Table 13.0 Trial 6: selection of mobile phase

Trial :6	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Methanol : Phosphate Buffer(80:20v/v)
Detection	300nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	Peaks detected but broad peaks observed

Fig 9.0 Trial 6: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Methanol: Phosphate Buffer(80:20v/v)

Table 14.0 Trial 7: Selection of Mobile Phase

Trial :7	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Chloroform: Acetonitrile (70:30v/v)
Detection	300nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute

Run Time	10 minutes
Observations:	One Peak detected but broad peak observe.

Fig 10.0 Trial 7: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Chloroform: Acetonitrile (70:30 v/v)

Table 15.0 Trial 8: Selection of Mobile Phase

TRIAL :8	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Chloroform: Acetonitrile (60:40v/v)
Detection	3000nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations	Peak detected but broad peaks observed

Fig 11.0 Trial 8: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Chloroform: Acetonitrile (60:40 v/v)

Table 16.0 Trial 9: selection of mobile phase

Trial :9	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Chloroform: Acetonitrile (50:50v/v)
Detection	300nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations	Peak detected and separated but broad peaks observed

Fig 12.0 Trial 9: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Chloroform: Acetonitrile(50:50v/v)

Table 17.0 Trial 10: selection of mobile phase

Trial :10	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: water (30:70v/v)

Detection	300nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	30 minutes
Observations	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)

Fig 13.0 Trial 10: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Acetonitrile: Water(30:70v/v)

Table 18.0 Trial 11: selection of mobile phase

Trial :11	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)
Mobile Phase	Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (55:25:25 v/v/v)
Detection	300nm

Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations	only one peak detected.

Fig 14.0 Trial 11: Chromatogram of Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride Methanol: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (55:25:25 v/v/v)

Table 19.0 Trial 12: selection of mobile phase

Trial :12	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (60:20:20 v/v/v)

Detection	300nm
Flow rate	1 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations	Peaks detected and separated, but broad peaks observe.

Fig 15.0 Trial 12: Chromatogram of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol Acetonitrile: Water (80:20v/v)

Table 20.0 Trial 13: selection of mobile phase

Trial :13	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μ m)
Mobile Phase	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (50:20:30 v/v/v)
Detection	300nm

Flow rate	1.5 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Observations	Good peaks with Adequate solution were observed.

Fig 16.0 Trial 13 Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std. Folic acid:3.215 min, Lysine Hydrochloride: 5.115 min

Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:

Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std. Folic acid:3.215 min, Lysine Hydrochloride: 5.115 min

Fig 17.0: Chromatogram of blank Methanol: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (50:20:30 v/v/v)

Chromatographic conditions for optimized mobile phase trial OF Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol

Table 23.0: optimized mobile phase trial of Folic Acid &Lysine Hydrochloride

Optimized Method	
Column	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 μm)

Mobile Phase	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (50:20:30 v/v/v)
Detection	300nm
Flow rate	1.5 mL/minute
Run Time	10 minutes
Detector	UV detector
Injection volume	10 μl
Column oven temperature	40°C
Mode:	ISOCRATIC

Fig 19.0: Optimized mobile phase trial for optimized chromatogram of Std Folic Acid :3.215 min Lysine Hydrochloride: 5.115 min

Introduction Of Method Validation Parameter:

Method validation is the process of documenting or proving that an analytical method provides analytical data acceptable for the intended use. The need to validate a method and the procedure to be followed are matters of professional judgement, although well-prescribed procedures and guidelines are now available that aid in decision making. According to that the various validation parameters to validate each and every above stated method are:

- Accuracy and Recovery
- Precision (Repeatability and Reproducibility)
- Linearity
- Range
- Robustness/ Ruggedness
- Limit of Detection (LOD)/ Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Accuracy and Recovery:

The capability of a procedure to generate outcomes close to the actual or standard value (Standard value may be reference value given in official compendia).

The chosen concentration for precision investigations must encompass the complete concentration range (i.e. one may the lowest concentration, one may the middle and one may be the last of range).

Accuracy is performed by performing recovery studies by spiking in 2 ways:

1. Spiking of sample with standard (in case placebo are not available).
2. Spiking of placebo with standard.

It can be performed at different level like 50, 100 and 150 % of test concentration or 80, 100, 120% of test concentration.

Reproducibility and Precision:

It is defined as the degree of similarity between test findings obtained from many samplings of the same sample. C.V. or relative standard deviation is capable of expressing it is further classified as reproducibility, repeatability, and intermediate precision. Repeatability is the capability of an analytical procedure to produce identical test findings when performed in a similar setting by the same operator over a brief period of time. It is

stated as R.S.D. when a minimum of three concentrations is analysed at least six times each, and R.S.D. is determined. At least 6 repetitions encompassing 100% of the target concentration or 9 repetitions covering the complete linear range must be assessed. (i.e., three replications for every concentration) Reproducibility is the capacity of an analytical procedure to yield same test findings when applied to identical samples under various conditions and by different analysts. Conditions of operation vary, but the variance is still within acceptable parameters. It is a crucial validation parameter if the procedure must be executed under diverse situations.

Range and Linearity:

It is the capability of the method to generate findings that are directly proportional to the concentration of a specific component in the samples. It is shown via certain mathematical modifications.

1. It may be conducted directly on the material being examined or using a suitable standard and dilution using the suggested approach.
2. It can be accomplished by measuring at least five injections in a series of standards. Eighty to one hundred twenty percent of the recommended concentration range is permissible.
3. A mathematical equation must illustrate the reaction of the sample to the concentration.
4. The linear regression approach requires a substantial zero intercept, and if it is not reached, one must demonstrate that there is no significant influence on accuracy.
5. Another method that may be applied is the response factor, which is generated by dividing the response by its corresponding

concentration to obtain the relative response. On a logarithmic scale, a graph showing relative reaction against concentration is presented. Therefore, the resultant horizontal line must be linear over the full range. Negative deviation is often observed at greater doses. On the graph, a horizontal line is drawn parallel to the x axis to represent 95 to 105 percent of the horizontal line. The reaction is linear with respect to concentration up until the intersection of the horizontal line and the 95 percent line.

6. It is the concentration interval between which quantitative analysis may be done with appropriate precision and linearity. The analytical method's range is stated in the same units (such as PPM or %).

Robustness:

A technique has the ability to be unaffected by tiny, purposeful changes to operating settings, but these changes are still within the method's range. The effects of these adjustments on the method's output are evaluated. By conducting robustness, one may assess if revalidation is necessary or not. Variable technique parameters include flow rate, mobile phase composition, mobile phase pH, and detection wavelength. This modification can be within the permissible range (i.e., 2% to 5% of the original value). The essential method parameter that identifies the susceptibility of the technique to change must be reported following ICH rules. However, it is not a registration requirement.

Robustness:

A technique has the ability to be unaffected by tiny, purposeful changes to operating settings, but these changes are still within the method's range. The effects of these adjustments on the method's output are evaluated. By conducting robustness,

one may assess if revalidation is necessary or not. Variable technique parameters include flow rate, mobile phase composition, mobile phase pH, and detection wavelength. This modification can be within the permissible range (i.e., 2% to 5% of the original value). The essential method parameter that identifies the susceptibility of the technique to change must be reported following ICH rules. However, it is not a registration requirement.

Limit of Quantification and Limit of Detection:

It refers to the analytical method's capacity to identify analyte in the presence of a matrix with sufficient accuracy and precision. The method may be able to detect the analyte but not quantify it. There may be confusion between technique sensitivity and LOD. Sensitivity can distinguish between minute differences in concentration. It may be described as the slope of the regression line.

Following methods are available other than signal to noise ratio that are as follows:

1. Visual determination: it is possible to determine by personally injecting the lowest known concentration that is detectable but cannot be measured by mathematical manipulations.
2. Standard deviation of response based on standard deviation of blank: it may be determined by examining the number of blank

samples and determining the standard deviation of the blank answers. This approach suggests the capability of a method to provide a response other than analyte concentration.

3. Using slope of regression line to estimate standard deviation of response: one may measure the S.D. of regression line of a given calibration curve or use S.D. of intercept.
4. It is also calculable using the mathematical formulae shown below.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Analytical method Validation

Linearity

For the purpose of linearity, accurately weighed amount of Folic acid (10 mg), and Lysine Hydrochloride (10 mg) was taken into the volumetric flask (10 ml) and volume of the flask was raised to 10 ml with methyl alcohol to give stock solution containing 100 µg/ml of Folic acid, and 100 µg/ml of Lysine Hydrochloride. Various aliquots from this stock solution were transferred to another 10 ml volumetric flask and volume was raised to the mark with mobile phase to give final solutions containing 0.5+35, 0.8+56, 1.0+70, 1.2+84 µg/ml and 1.5+105 µg/ml of Folic acid and Lysine Hydrochloride respectively.

Table 24.0 Linearity data for Folic Acid

Linearity level	Conc. (µg/ml)	FOLIC ACID		
		Mean Area	± SD (n=5)	% RSD
50 % Linearity	0.5	162606	162606± 354.94	0.22
75% Linearity	0.8	266614	266614± 2844.91	1.07
100% Linearity	1.0	323891	323891± 2629.41	0.81
125% Linearity	1.2	387361	387361± 2278.43	0.59
150% Linearity	1.5	487099	487099± 1083.92	0.51

Table 25.0 Linearity data for Lysine Hydrochloride

Linearity level	Conc. (µg/ml)	Mean Area	± SD (n=5)	% RSD
50% Linearity	35.0	303109	303109 ± 3370.21	1.11
75% Linearity	56.0	481026	481026± 2240.21	0.57
100% Linearity	70.0	607529	607529± 2927.73	0.48
125% Linearity	84.0	729227	729227± 4888.17	0.67
150% Linearity	105.0	911747	911747± 6113.45	0.67

Fig 20.0: Overlain Linearity Spectra of Folic Acid and Lysine Hydrochloride

Fig 21.0: Calibration curve of Folic Acid

Fig 22.0: Calibration curve of Lysine Hydrochloride

Table 26.0 Linearity results for Folic Acid and Lysine Hydrochloride

Regression Analysis	Folic acid	Lysine Hydrochloride
Concentration Range	0.5-1.5 μ g/mL	35-105 μ g/mL
Regression equation	$y = 321373x + 4141.8$	$y = 8718.2x - 3749.8$
Correlation co-efficient	0.9993	0.9999

Precision

R.S.D For Repeatability data was found to be 0.64 % for Folic acid and 0.45 % for Lysine Hydrochloride.

Repeatability

The data for repeatability for Folic acid and Lysine Hydrochloride is shown in table 27.0. The %

Table 27.0 Repeatability data for Folic Acid and Lysine Hydrochloride

Drugs	Conc. (μ g/ml)	Mean Peak Area \pm SD	%RSD
Folic acid	1	466878.4 \pm 2989.2	0.64
Lysine Hydrochloride	70	705279.61 \pm 3208.55	0.45

Inter-day precision

found to be 0.36-0.79% for Folic acid and 0.13 - 0.41 % for Lysine Hydrochloride.

The data for interday precision for Folic acid and Lysine Hydrochloride is shown in table 28.0 & 29.0 The % R.S.D for intraday precision was

Inter-Day Precision for Folic Acid:

Table 28.0 Inter-day precision data for estimation Folic Acid

Level	μ g/mL	Area	Mean	SD	RSD
50%	0.5	164879	164579.3	608.6052	0.369794
		163879			
		164980			

100%	1.0	324768	327088	2587.849	0.791178
		326617			
		329879			
150%	1.5	482354	485136	2410.329	0.496836
		486598			
		486456			
Folic acid			Lysine Hydrochloride		

Inter-Day Precision for Lysine Hydrochloride:**Table 29.0 Inter-day precision data for estimation of Lysine Hydrochloride**

Level	µg/mL	Area	Mean	SD	RSD
50%	35	303462	304515	1042.174	0.342241
		304537			
		305546			
100%	70	604378	604606.7	253.3384	0.041901
		604563			
		604879			
150%	105	912365	913053.3	1211.331	0.132668
		914452			
		912343			

Intra-day precision:

The data for intra-day precision for Folic acid and Lysine Hydrochloride is shown in table 9.5. The %

R.S.D for intraday precision was found to be 0.47-1.01 % for Folic acid and 0.11 – 0.24 % for Lysine Hydrochloride.

Table 30.0 Intra-day precision data for estimation of Folic Acid and Lysine Hydrochloride

Mcg/ml	0.5	1.0	1.5	35	70	105
	165490	325682	487690	303757	604768	912345
	167860	327689	483452	304522	603562	916578
	168790	328706	487690	303425	603568	913342
MEAN	167380	327359	486277.3	303901.3	603966	914088.3
± SD	1701.558	1538.772	2446.81	562.5623	694.5589	2212.992
RSD	1.016584	0.470056	0.503172	0.185113	0.115	0.242098

Accuracy:

Accuracy of the method was confirmed by recovery study from synthetic mixture at three level standard additions. Percentage recovery for

Folic acid & Lysine Hydrochloride was found to be 99.48- 99.78% and 99.33-100.59 % respectively. The results are shown in table 31.0-32.0.

Recovery For Dapagliflozin:**Table 32.0 Recovery data for Dapagliflozin**

Recovery Level	mg added	Mg recovered	% Recovery	Mean (%)
	5.02	5.00	99.60	

50%	5.02	4.99	99.40	99.87
	5.02	5.05	100.60	
100%	10.05	9.99	99.40	99.60
	10.05	10.06	100.10	
	10.05	9.98	99.30	
150%	15.20	15.45	101.64	101.23
	15.20	15.31	100.72	
	15.20	15.40	101.32	

Recovery For Bisoprolol:

Table 33.0 Recovery data for Bisoprolol

Recovery Level	mg added	Mg recovered	% Recovery	Mean (%)
50%	2.51	2.48	98.80	100.00
	2.51	2.53	100.80	
	2.51	2.52	100.40	
100%	5.10	5.02	98.43	98.43
	5.10	5.03	98.63	
	5.10	5.01	98.24	
150%	7.54	7.51	99.60	99.87
	7.54	7.52	99.73	
	7.54	7.56	100.27	

LOD and LOQ:

The limit of detection (LOD) and Limit of Quantification (LOQ) was found to be as per below:

Table 34.0 LOD and LOQ Limit for Lysine Hydrochloride & Folic Acid

Folic acid		Lysine Hydrochloride	
LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOD($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	LOQ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)
2.40	3.15	1.30	2.55

Robustness:

The method is found to be robust as the results were not significantly affected by slight variation in Mobile Phase Composition and flow rate of

mobile phase. The results are shown in table 35.0. Variation seen was within the acceptable range respect to peak asymmetry and theoretical plates, so the method was found to be robust.

Table 35.0 Robustness data for Folic Acid & Lysine Hydrochloride

Parameter	Level of Change	Effect on assay volume			
		Folic acid		Lysine Hydrochloride	
		Assay \pm SD	RSD	Assay \pm SD	RSD
Flow rate	1.0 mL/min	99.70 \pm 0.50	0.49	99.92 \pm 0.48	0.48
	1.1 mL/min	101.09 \pm 0.72	0.72	99.99 \pm 0.83	0.83
Mobile phase composition	25:75	99.47 \pm 0.53	0.53	100.22 \pm 1.43	1.43
	27:73	99.39 \pm 0.99	0.98	100.04 \pm 1.06	1.06
	23:77	99.51 \pm 0.67	0.67	99.45 \pm 0.77	0.78

Analysis of marketed product:

which is comparable with the corresponding label claim.

The proposed method was successfully applied to analysis of the commercially available tablet formulation. The % drugs were found satisfactory,

Table 36.0 Analysis of marketed formulations

Table 36.0 Analysis of Marketed Formulations

Drug	Amount taken (µg/mL)	Amount found (µg/mL)	% Assy
Folic acid	1	9.93±0.04	99.80 ±1.20
Lysine Hydrochloride	70	8.03 ±0.10	100.70±1.07

Summary Of Method Validation:

Summary of validation parameter are shown in below table. All the parameters for substance met the criteria of ICH guideline for the method validation and found to be suitable for routine quantitative analysis in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The result of linearity, accuracy, precision

proved to be within limits with lower limits of detection and quantification. Robustness of method was confirmed as no significant in the were observed on analysis by subjecting the method to slight change in the method condition. Assay results obtained by proposed method are fair agreement.

Table 37.0 Summary of validation parameter of RP-HPLC method

Optimized chromatographic Condition	
Stationary Phase	C-18 (id 4.6 x 250 mm, 5 µm)
Mobile Phase	Methanol: Acetonitrile: Phosphate buffer (50:20:30 v/v/v)
Detection wave Length	300 nm
Flow rate	1 ml/minute
Run time	10 minutes
Retention Time	Folic acid: 3.215 min, Lysine Hydrochloride:5.115 min.

Table 38.0 Validation Parameters

Validation Parameters				
Parameter	Limit	Result		Conclusion
		Folic acid	Lysine Hydrochloride	
Linearity and Range	R2> 0.995	0.9993 (0.5-1.5µg/mL)	0.999 (35-105µg/mL)	Method was linear
Repeatability	RSD<2	0.31-1.54	0.10-0.87	Method was repeatable
LOD	-	2.40	3.40	-
LOQ	-	1.30	2.55	-
Intra-day Precision	RSD<2	0.36-0.79%	0.13 -0.41 %	Method was precise
Inter-Day Precision	RSD<2	0.47-1.01 %	0.11 – 0.24 %	Method was precise
% Recovery	98-102%	99.35 ±0.83– 100.01±0.03 %	100.22±0.21 – 100.78±0.23%	Method was accurate
Robustness	RSD<2	0.41– 0.63	0.40-0.91	Method was robust

Assay%		99.80 ±1.20	100.70±1.07	-
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CONCLUSION:

A simple, economic, specific, accurate and precise RP-HPLC method for simultaneous estimation of dapagliflozin propanediol monohydrate and bisoprolol fumarate in synthetic mixture. All method validation parameters lie within its acceptance criteria as per ICH Q2(R1) guideline so we can conclude that methods are specific, linear, accurate and precise. In RP-HPLC method, Linearity was observed in the concentration range of Dapagliflozin 5-15 µg/ml and Bisoprolol 2.5-7.5 µg/ml with correlation coefficient of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol 0.998 & 0.999. The proposed method was successfully applied for the simultaneous estimation of both drugs in combined dosage form. The Assay value of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol was found to be 99.30% & 100.60%. The Mean recovery was found to be in the range Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol of 99.87 – 101.23% & 99.87 – 100.0%. LOD and LOQ were found to be Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol of 2.40 µg/ml and 3.15 µg/ml & 1.30 µg/ml and 2.55 µg/ml. The % RSD of repeatability precision, intra-day precision & inter-day precision of Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol was found to be 0.64% & 0.45%, 0.18-0.34% & 0.06-0.70%, 0.05-0.69% & 0.19-0.40%. It indicated that the method is precise. The % RSD of Robustness change in Flow rate Dapagliflozin & Bisoprolol was found to be 0.041%-0.63% & 0.40%-0.91. Hence, proposed method is well suited for simultaneous estimation in synthetic mixture. It can be easily and conveniently adopted for routine analysis of semi solid dosage form.

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HOW TO CITE: Rajdeep Dodiya*, Dhirendra Kumar Tarai, Khyati Bhupta, Dr. Santosh Kirtane, Epidemiology, Development and Validation of RP-HPLC Method For Simultaneous Estimation of Folic Acid and Lysine Hydrochloride in Their Combined Oral Liquid Formulation, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 6, 3595-3617.
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